

SPOTLIGHTS ON THE ARCHITECTURE OF MARGELAN MOSQUES IN UZBEKISTAN (13 – 14TH A.H / 19 – 20TH A.D) CENTURIES

Mahmoud Roshdy

Islamic Department, Faculty of Archaeology, Cairo University, Egypt

ABSTRACT

City of Margilan is considered one of the most important cities in the Republic of Uzbekistan that having a lot of different architectural monuments , some of them still remain ,others were destroyed by Russian invasion so we don't know a lot about them , despite their great number the city didn't have the same fame of the other cities in Central Asia such as Bukhara ,Samarqand , Khiva and Tashkent . In addition the period of Manghit rule (1200-1338 A.H / 1785 – 1920 A.D) had a lot of mosques that showing the flourishing of architectural activity that arise our interest to study the architecture of the mosques of that period as well as making a comparison with other cities , the contemporary and previous in Uzbekistan that reflecting creations and architectural traditions of Ferghana valley , in addition it shows the skills of architects and artists that having a high degree of skill in matching the buildings with the environment nature in Central Asia as well as the variety in architectural and decorative units .

KEYWORDS

Uzbekistan , Margilan , Mosque , Mihrab , Arch

1. INTRODUCTION

City of Margilan (Al-Hamawi, 1908) in Uzbekistan (Abu Al- Elaa , 1992) (Ahmed,1992) had an important architectural style (Fig. 1) in the period of Manghit (Abu Al- Elaa , 1992) resulted in a mixture between summer system and winter system in mosques , as the system of the open court and porticos proved to be useless during snow season , in addition the system of closed mosques proved to be useless during summer season . So we find in Margilan and in most cities in Central Asia (Partold ,1996) later the system of a mosque that consisted of a closed prayer hall used in winter and outer riwaqs surrounded it provided with mihrabs used for prayer in summer. This type of plan prevailed in (10 A.H – 16 A.D) the it became the main style in all cities of Central Asia up till now (Rizq , 2008) .

2. PLAN

Mosques of Margilan dated back (13 – 14 A.H / 19 – 20 A.D). Those mosques consisted of a closed prayer hall "winter mosque " and outer riwaqs " summer mosque " we can divide this style into two types

2.1. THE FIRST TYPE

Winter mosque and summer mosque at the same axis. Those mosques consisted of a rectangular area extending from north to south divided into two sections: closed prayer hall “winter mosque” and outer riwaqs “summer mosque “at the same axis. The mosque was divided into a rectangular area, the interior consisted of a group of riwaqs two or three formed by wooden columns that support wooden roofs decorated by Arabesque (Abd Al-Aziz , 2003) . The south western side at the two mosques had a stucco mihrab in the middle consisted of a niche with pointed arch.

The entry to the winter mosque through a door opening or two doors at the north western side as in the mosque of Khoga Bursa (13 A.H – 19 A.D) (Fig. 2) (Fig . 8,9,10) and at the south eastern side as in the mosque of Moeen Mubarak (1327 – 1328 A.H / 1909 – 1910 A.D) (Fig . 3) (Fig. 11,12,13) mosque of Shekar (14 A.H / 20 A.D) (Fig. 4) (Pl. 14, 15). This type appeared in the mosque of Muzafar Khan (13 A.H /19 A.D) in Al-Naqshband foyer in Bukhara (Fig. 5).

2.2. SECOND TYPE

Consists of a closed prayer hall (winter mosque) surrounded by the summer mosque through riwaqs at two directions: the north eastern and the south eastern, both of them consist of one riwaq through a row of wooden columns that support wooden roofs. at the middle of the south western side at north western direction there are three niches, the middle one the stucco mihrab and the other two niches are two rectangular openings leading to the interior of winter mosque while at the south eastern side of south eastern direction we find a door opening leading to the interior of winter mosque that takes the plan of a rectangular area divided into two riwaqs through a row of wooden columns support the wooden roofs. In the middle of the south western side a mihrab made of stucco with a pointed arch as in the mosque of Sherman Baz (1344 – 1353 A.H / 1925 – 1934 A.D) . (Fig. 6) (Fig. 16, 17 , 18) .

This type appeared in the north of India in Bengal where the weather was close to the weather in Central Asia and Bukhara that was cold with snow in winter and hot in summer so there were a lot of examples appeared in Bengal " Bangladesh " as the mosque of Sham Kati dated back to the ninth A.H / fifteenth A.D century characterized by a shed in front of prayer hall at the east, the prayer hall is a closed square covered by a dome.

This type was found also in Anatolia as the mosque of Surgali dated back to the seventh A.H / thirteenth A.D century (Fig.7) that consists of a square prayer hall with a shed in front of it at the east. That kind of shed in front of the closed prayer hall was found also in Egypt at the mosque of al-Sayeda Roqia dated back to 6th A.H / 12th A.D consists of a prayer hall of three squares , the middle square covered with a dome with a shed in front of it at the west but here the shed was used for funerary prayers as the mosque is close to tombs area .

This plan was found also before in Tunisia at the mosque of Abi Qatada dated back to 3th A.H / 9th A.D consists of a prayer hall with four squares in the middle divided it into nine squares like the prayer hall at the mosque of Um Khawaja Bahaa Al- Din Naqshaband but at the mosque of Abi Qatada there is one shed or one riwaq only in front of the mosque at the west as in the mosque of Baland (Rizq , 2007) , the mosque of Al –Sedeqeen (" 1209 A.H / 1795 A.D) that was a domed mosque surrounded by two riwaqs at the north and the east , as well as the mosque of Fathallah Bay (1290 A.H /1873 A.D) a domed mosque surrounded by two riwaqs at the north

and the east , in addition to the mosque of Mir Ibrahim (the late of 13th A.H / 19th A.D) consists of a rectangular area without riwaqs and from outside surrounded by two riwaqs at the north and east (Rizq , 2008) .

3. ARCHITECTURAL ELEMENTS

They varied in mosques among wooden roofs, wooden columns, mihrabs , arches , stalactites " and doors came as follow

3.1. WOODEN CEILINGS

Represented in flat roofs divided into rectangular areas or square areas with extending wooden frame beneath the roof of the mosque , each area divided into wooden beams of coloured cane , some of them were decorated with coloured floral ornaments and geometrical forms as in the mosque of Khoja Bursa (13 A.H / 19 A.D) , mosque of Moeen Mubarak (1327 - 1328 A.H / 1909 – 1910 A.D) , mosque of Sherman Baz (1344 – 1353 A.H / 1925 – 1934 A.D) and mosque of Shikar (14th A .H / 20th A . D century).

We have a lot of wooden roofs that covered the mosques of Central Asia since the fourth A.H century – the twentieth A.D century, among them the mosque of Aroos al-Falak built by sultan Mahmoud Al – Ghuznawi as well as some mosques of Qura Khaneen with wooden columns in Central Asia. Then mosques covered by wooden roofs supported by columns appeared , that dated back to (9 – 10 A.H / 15 – 16 A.D) for example the mosque of Al-Khawaja Ahrar dated back to (9 A.H / 15 A.D) in Tashkent (Al-Narshakhi ,1993) (Shaker, 1987) .

3.2. MIHRABS

Architectural buildings included collections of mihrabs that located at the level of qipla wall at the south western side. Those buildings characterized by the plurality of their mihrabs. A mosque often included a mihrab in the middle of winter prayer hall rather than another mihrab at the summer mosque. Those mihrabs were hollowed with pentagonal plan, and some of them with rectangular plan.

Mihrabs were hollowed crowned by pointed arch without columns supported the arch but it was supported firstly on a part of the wall of the niche extending beneath it with a base like a bell. Those mihrabs were simple, a few of them with decorations represented in a row of surd arcade at the first level of the mihrab.

3.3. WOODEN COLUMNS

They were used in buildings to support wooden roofs. Their general shape was carved to be decreased up wards (Benkie , 1968 . Some of them had ribbed conical bases, a lot of them without decorations. This conical base supported the body of the column that having a decorative design beginning with a decorative lobed arch. Sometimes the body was bare or decorated with ornamented bands extending vertically to the top of the column (Ebaid , Roshdy , 2013).

3.4. STALACTITES

It's one of the most important architectural & decorative elements that were at the top of wooden columns. Most of them the type of pointed arches with pendants. Central Asia used stalactites as a decorative element in buildings so we find them for example at the dome of Gur Amir (1051 – 1071 A.H/ 1641 – 1660 A.D) in Samarkand , and at the madrasa of Shir Dar (1029 – 1046 A.H/ 1619 – 1636 A.D) , the madrasa of Tila Carey (1057 – 1071 A.H/ 1647 – 1660 A.D) in Samarkand , the madrasa of Abd Al-Aziz Khan (1062 – 1063 A.H/ 1651 – 1652 A.D) , the madrasa of Mir Arab (942 – 946 A.H/ 1535 – 1539 A.D) in Bukhara.

3.5. ARCHES

They were used in mosques as a decorative element not as architectural element where artists used the arch to decorate some of buildings especially at the first level of mihrabs bodies. Arches varied between lobed arches and pointed arches , with the shape of bare arcade or decorated arches with various floral ornaments or rectangular areas divided into pointed and lobed arches in different sizes made of stucco .

3.6. DOORS

They are considered one of architectural & functional elements in buildings, they are elements of movement and communication, and through them we reach the architectural units in the institution. Most doors followed the style of two shutters (Ebaid , Roshdy ,2012) but different in sizes. the suite consists of three rectangular plates was the most in use for decorating doors , two plates were narrow up and down , the third one was large extending vertically between them , sometimes the opposite. This type was the most common in Central Asia at that time.

3.7. FIGURES

Figure 1. Map of Margilan in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Figure 2. The plan of the mosque of Khoja Bursa " 13th A.H /19th A.D " .

Figure 3. The plan of the mosque Moeen Mubarak "1327 – 1328 A.H /1909 – 1910 A.D

Figure 4. The plan of the mosque of Shikar "14th A.H / 20th A.D century ".

Figure 5. The plan of the mosque of Muzafar Khan in Bukhara “13th A.H / 19th A.D century “.

Figure 6. The plan of the mosque of Shir Baz “1344 – 1353 A.H / 1925 – 1934 A.D “.

Figure 7. The plan of the mosque of Surgali in Konya “7th A.H / 13th A.D century

Figure 8. The main façade of the mosque of Khoja Bursa “13th A.H / 19th A.D century “.

Figure 9. The summer mosque in the mosque of Khoja Bursa “13th A.H /19th A.D century

Figure 10. The winter mosque in the mosque of Khoja Bursa “13th A.H /19th A.D century“.

Figure 11. The main façade of the mosque of Moeen Mubarak “1327 – 1328 A.H/1909 – 1910 A.D “.

Figure 12. The summer mosque in the mosque of Moeen Mubarak “1327 – 1328 A.H/1909 – 1910 A.D “.

Figure 13: The winter mosque in the mosque of Moeen Mubarak “1327 – 1328 A.H/1909 – 1910 A.D “.

Figure 14 . The main façade in the mosque of Shikar “14th A.H / 20th A.D century “.

Figure 15 . The summer mosque in the mosque of Shikar “14th A.H / 20th A.D century “.

Figure 16. The main façade of the mosque of Shir Baz “1343 – 1344 A.H / 1934 – 1925 A.D “.

Figure 17. The summer mosque in the mosque of Shir Baz “1344 – 1353 A.H / 1925 – 1934 A.D “.

Figure 18 . The winter mosque in the mosque of Shir Baz “1344 – 1353 A.H /1925 – 1934 A.D “.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Uzbekistan” we can conclude a number of facts and results as follow:-

- The study proved that the style of “winter mosque” " summer mosque “became the main style in Marghlan specially and in all cities of Central Asia generally since the beginning of 10th A.H/ 16th A.D century till the 14th/ 20th A.D century .
- The study confirmed that the main style was divided into two main types as follow :- The first type: the winter and summer mosque at the same axis. That type consists of a rectangular area extending from north to south divided into two sections: winter mosque and summer mosque at the same axis. The second type: the winter mosque surrounded by the summer mosque through riwaqs at the north eastern and south eastern directions, each of them consists of one riwaq through a row of wooden columns.
- The study proved that the multiplicity of mihrabs in the mosques of Marghlan specially during the period of (13 – 14th A.H / 19 – 20th A.D) , where most mosques included two mihrabs one for the winter mosque to gather worshipers at winter prayer hall during winter season , and another for summer season at the outer shed .

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AUTHORS

Working as teaching asisstant in the department of Islamic Archaeology – Faculty of Archaeology – Cairo University – 2007 – 2011 A.D . Working as asisstant lecturer in the department of Islamic Archaeology – Faculty of Archaeology – Cairo University 2012 : 2014 A.D . Working as a lecturer since 2014 A.D up till now . Working in Excavations field school of islamic archaeology , held in Excavations site " Cairo walls " that teaching digging methods , excavations , studying of layers , architectural drawing , study of islamic pottery and ceramic with the French mission 2011 A.D .

